

TAPIS SYSTEMS ENABLE COLLABORATIVE DATA MANAGEMENT IN SCIENCE GATEWAYS

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SCIENCE GATEWAYS: OVERVIEW

- ▶ Science Gateways are user interfaces connecting researchers with HPC systems
- ▶ Support the research lifecycle from data collection to analysis to publication
- ▶ Science is COLLABORATIVE! Science gateways must support this collaboration.
- ▶ TACC maintains a Core infrastructure for spinning up containerized gateways

Science Gateways at TACC

SHARED WORKSPACES: USER PERSPECTIVE

- ▶ Shared Workspaces provide a space within a science gateway for collaborative data management
- ▶ Users can add team members to a workspace and manage permissions
- ▶ Files uploaded to Shared Workspaces can be staged as inputs to HPC jobs
- ▶ Included with each Core gateway deployment

SHARED WORKSPACES: USER PERSPECTIVE

Shared Workspaces / [acl-job-confirm](#)

[Extract](#) [Compress](#) [Rename](#) [Move](#) [Copy](#) [Download](#) [Trash](#)

[+ Add](#)

- My Data (Frontera Home)
- My Data (Frontera Scratch)
- My Data (Work)
- Shared Workspaces**
- Google Drive

acl-job-confirm [Edit Descriptions](#) | [Manage Team](#)

Search acl-job-confirm **Filter:** [All Files Types](#)

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Size	Last Modified	Path
<input type="checkbox"/>	JAR_pearc22_01.png	131.6 kB	04/14/2022 10:53	View Path
<input type="checkbox"/>	aclconfirmfolder	4.0 kB	01/19/2023 12:06	View Path
<input type="checkbox"/>	testfolder	4.0 kB	03/28/2023 15:44	View Path
<input type="checkbox"/>	testfolder2	4.0 kB	03/28/2023 15:49	View Path

SHARED WORKSPACES: USER PERSPECTIVE

The screenshot shows a 'Manage Team' dialog box for a workspace named 'acl-job-confirm'. The dialog has a title bar with a close button (X) and a '+ Add' button. Below the title bar, there is an 'Add Member' section with an 'Add' button and a search input field labeled 'Search by name'. The main area of the dialog is a table with two columns: 'Members' and 'Role'. The table lists two members: Jake Rosenberg (jrosenb@tacc.utexas.edu) with the role 'Owner', and Sal Tijerina (stijerina@tacc.utexas.edu) with the role 'User (read/write)'. There is a 'Remove' button next to Sal Tijerina's entry. At the bottom of the dialog, there is a 'Change Ownership' link. In the background, a table with a 'Path' column is partially visible, showing entries like '53 View Path', '06 View Path', '44 View Path', and '49 View Path'.

acl-job-confirm [Edit Descriptions](#) | [Manage Team](#)

Manage Team

Add Member

Add Search by name

Members	Role
Jake Rosenberg jrosenb (jrosenb@tacc.utexas.edu)	Owner
Sal Tijerina sal (stijerina@tacc.utexas.edu)	User (read/write) Remove

[Change Ownership](#)

Path

53 [View Path](#)

06 [View Path](#)

44 [View Path](#)

49 [View Path](#)

SHARED WORKSPACES: CHALLENGES

- ▶ Permissions: Need to support modifying/revoking privileges as well as transferring ownership
- ▶ Can't assume our backend will have sudo access!
- ▶ Users access data through the gateway as well as through SSH

SHARED WORKSPACES: IMPLEMENTATION

- ▶ Implementation relies on Tapis: cross-institution API for managing HPC systems
- ▶ Tapis Systems abstract physical machines: compute and storage resources
- ▶ Permissions on systems managed through the Security Kernel

SHARED WORKSPACES: IMPLEMENTATION

SHARED WORKSPACES: IMPLEMENTATION

- ▶ Each Shared Workspace is a Tapis system that maps to a directory on Corral (40PB storage resource) e.g. /workspace-1234
- ▶ Files are owned by TACC service account, but the security kernel gives users permission to upload/modify files via Tapis, and grant those permissions to others
- ▶ Permissions are synced with ACLs on the physical file system (via Tapis), so users can perform bulk operations using SCP/Globus

SHARED WORKSPACES: IMPLEMENTATION

